

Earthworms as indicators of soil health in arable fields

Problem

Earthworms can be used to assess soil degradation and poor soil-structure induced by compaction, loss of organic matter and poor residue breakdown. This indicator can also inform on unstable and declining crop performance

Solution

Earthworm surveys can be carried out in arable fields as they can be a biological indicator of soil health and a way to assess management impacts in real time.

Benefits

They act as a biological diagnostic to confirm, or help explain a functional problem in the soil and results can be seen real time over a period if management practices change

Practical recommendation

- Earthworm surveys require minimal equipment and expertise and are suitable for farmers, landowners, and citizen scientists.
- Low earthworm numbers indicate poor soil biological activity and impaired soil function that may be linked to compaction, intensive cultivation, low organic matter or chemical pressures. This results in poor soil structure, less movement of water and nutrients that can potentially affect crop performance in a negative manner such as poor growth and yields
- Earthworm populations show recovery within 1-3 years after positive management changes such as reduced tillage, but this is also dependent on soil type, climate and the disturbance history (worms in fields that were previously used to grow potatoes typically took 3 years to begin to recover).

Protocol

- Dig out a pit (square - size of a spade width ~ 20 cm) and place soil on white mat or tray
- Hand sort soil and place all worms in a container, washing soil off with some water if necessary
- Record the number of juveniles and return to pit – juveniles do not have a saddle (visible thickened ring located near the head only on adult earth worms)

Applicability box

Theme

Soil health using earthworms as biological indicators

Keywords

Surface (Epigeic), Topsoil (Endogeic), and Deep burrowers (Anecic), Soil Health, Adults, Juveniles, Casts, Middens

Context

Whichever arable field needs assessing

Application time

Before sowing in Spring and after harvest in the Autumn

Required time

Approx 10 minutes per soil pit from start to finish

Period of impact

Usually a timescale greater than 1 year for any change in practices to begin to be seen in earthworm populations

Equipment

No machinery; spade, white mat/tray, container for worms, recording sheet, ruler, labels and camera

Best in

Any field when soil is damp preferably after rain

- Place ruler and sample point/date label next to adult worm and record adults in each functional group in a notebook or recording form as follows:

Juveniles: no saddle

Adults: with saddle

Adult functional groups: 3 types

Surface worms

Size: small (matchstick, <8mm),
Colour: red
Habit: fast moving, found in leaf litter

Epigeic worms

Topsoil worms

Size: small-medium
Colour: pink, grey, green, mottled yellow
Habit: most common, found in topsoil

Endogeic worms

Deep burrowers

Size: large (>8mm)
Colour: red or black head
Habit: large, vertical burrows, middens

Anecic worms

- Deep burrowing earthworms feed on leaves in the soil that they drag into vertical burrows in the soil and cast on the surface (nutrient rich excrement). Casts are the result of digesting soil and organic matter and will increase aeration and nutrient recycling in soil. Some anecic species may make middens (piles of casts, leaves or twigs) around the entrances to their burrows. Middens act as a plug to protect the burrow from drying out and the elements.
- Topsoil worms can produce casts, whilst surface worms rarely make casts in mineral soil.

Photographs showing a dugout soil pit on the left and measurement of worms on right along whilst also categorizing them as juvenile worms or adult worms

Further information

- Earthworms Author: Joanna Uglow – Earthworms, <https://fwagsw.org.uk/earthworms/>

About this practice abstract

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LegumES – Valorization of ecosystem services provided by legume crops - aims to share, showcase, co-develop, and implement the knowledge, key agronomic practices, methodologies, and tools which will allow optimized legume-based systems, and valorization of the ES benefits provided.

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